

Efficacy of Copper Plus WP against Tomato Late Blight, Early Blight, Bacterial Spot, and Powdery Mildew at Arba Minch and Mihirab Abaya in Southern Region, Ethiopia

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Abstract

The study was carried out under rain-fed conditions with supplementary irrigation at Arba Minch and Mihirab Abaya in SNNPRs in 2021 to evaluate the efficacy of Copper Plus WP relative to another promising standard check bactericide, Copper oxide 77% WP, for the management of bacterial spot, late blight, early blight, and powdery mildew in tomato for registration purposes. The study consisted of three treatments and was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Results showed that application of bactericide/fungicide at 14-day intervals significantly reduced mean bacterial spot (23.39%), late blight (14.90%), early blight (32.73%), and powdery mildew (9.53%) severities in the three locations. Bacterial spot, late blight, early blight, and powdery mildew had the lowest mean AUDPC values across locations, at 234.78,

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297.82, 518.62, and 120.08%-days, respectively. Plots sprayed with candidate chemical had the highest mean (30,150.05 kg ha⁻¹) marketable fruit output among the three locations. In comparison to Copper oxide 77% WP in every location, Copper Plus WP significantly reduced the epidemic development of a bacterial spot, late blight, early blight, and powdery mildew, which in turn increased tomato fruit yield. It is therefore advised to register Copper Plus WP for the treatment of these diseases as it was discovered to be quite efficient.

Keywords: AUDPC; bactericide/fungicide; bacterial spot; early blight; fruit yield; late blight; powdery mildew; severity; tomato.

1. Introduction

“Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) is an important vegetable crop grown worldwide” (Bauchet & Causse, 2012). “It is widely produced both during the rainy and dry seasons under supplemental irrigation in Ethiopia” (Tsedeke, 2007; Derbew *et al.*, 2012). “The crop is grown for its fruits, which are used in salads or cooked as a vegetable, in processed form as tomato paste, tomato sauce, ketchup and juice, and the ripe fruits are rich in nutrients, minerals and vitamins” (USDA, 2005). “Similarly, the crop is consumed in fresh and processed forms; the importance of tomato is increasing as it a high-value commodity crop, which has been given top priority in vegetable research in Ethiopia” (Tsedeke, 2007). “However, the national average yield of tomato in the country is very low (12.52 t ha⁻¹) as compared to the world (32.80 t ha⁻¹)” (Anonymous, 2011), which is less than 44.32% of the world average. “Lower production and productivity of the crop than its potential is mostly attributed to numerous pests, which cause serious damage on the yield in the world. The major diseases that affected tomato production include early blight (*Alternaria solani*), late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*), bacterial spot (*Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *vesicatoria*) and powdery mildew (*Leveillula taurica*)” as reported by Tesfaye & Habtu (1986) “These are the most widespread and pressing problems to subsistence tomato-growing farmers and private investors in the country. Under field conditions, sometimes several diseases come simultaneously at the same time if there are a favorable environment, a susceptible host, and virulent pathogens” (Agrios, 2005). “Yield loss due to these aforementioned diseases was estimated to be 15 to 100% of the total production of tomato” (McCarter *et al.*, 1983). Therefore, measures to reduce sources of infection and prevent the spread of disease are of great importance in controlling tomato.

“Since most of the tomato cultivars grown by the small-scale farmers and investors in the region and country as well are susceptible to the target disease and causing considerable yield loss particularly where the climates favor the development of these diseases. Thus, there is a need for alternative and effective bactericide and fungicides through the introduction of a new fungicide or different formulations of the existing bactericides and fungicides with the same active ingredient that may continue to be introduced by the pesticide companies. However, the efficacy of the newly introduced bactericides and fungicides on bacterial spot, late blight, early blight and powdery mildew of the tomato crop should be regularly tested and verified before introducing to the production systems. Because the efficacy of bactericide/fungicide is highly influenced by environmental factors, pathogens' inoculum load, time of application and rates of fungicide” (Tefaye & Habtu (1986)). Based on the above background, Arba Minch Agricultural Research Center has been designated by the Ministry of Agriculture through Southern Agricultural Research Institute to test the efficacy of Copper Plus WP, against bacterial spot, late blight, early blight and powdery mildew of tomato during the 2021 cropping season. Therefore, the objective of the verification trial was to evaluate the efficacy of Copper Plus WP (Copper oxychloride 30% + Azoxystrobin 10%) relative to another promising standard check bactericide, Copper oxide 77% WP, for the management of bacterial spot, late blight, early blight and powdery mildew in tomato for registration purposes.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Descriptions of the Study Site

The study was carried out under rain-fed conditions with supplementary of irrigation during the 2021 main cropping season at Arba Minch (Chano mile and Chano Chalba *kebeles*) and Mihirab Abaya (Fura *kebele*) in SNNPRs. The sites are found at an elevation of 1211 (Chano Mile), 1218 (Chano Chalba) and 1108 (Fura)

meters above sea level. Bimodal rainfall pattern is the major characteristic of the study area, short rainy season (March and April), and the main rainy season (mid-August to mid-November). The areas received a total annual rainfall and average temperatures during the 2021 cropping season were 750 mm and 27.28 °C, respectively.

2.2 Treatments, Design of Experiment and Trial Management

Copper Plus WP at the rate of 1 kg/ha with 400 L water (Candidate fungicide), Copper oxide 77% WP at the rate of 2 kg/ha with 200 L water (Standard check), and unsprayed check were used. The total width and length of the layout were designed at 35 x 33 m with a unit plot size of 10 x 10 m, respectively. A spacing of 1.5 and 2.5 m was left to separate each plot and block, respectively, to prevent the drift or cross-contamination of the fungicides. The treatments comprised of Copper Plus WP, Copper oxide WP and unsprayed control. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Tomato seedlings were transplanted on 20, 24 and 29 July 2021 at Chano Chalba, Fura and Chano Mile *kebeles*, respectively. Transplanting was done with spacing of 100 and 30 cm inter- and intra-rows, respectively. There were 10 rows per plot and the middle eight rows were used for data collection. A recommended fertilizer rate of 150 kg ha⁻¹ NPS was applied in rows at transplanting and 100 kg urea ha⁻¹ was used by split application as side-dressing at transplanting and early flowering stage during the growing period. Supplementary irrigation, weeding and cultivation were performed manually whenever they were necessary in the three locations during the growing period. For the candidate pesticide, the use of the rates per hectare and amount of water for mixing was performed as suggested by the manufacturer. Spraying was performed using a manual knapsack sprayer calibrated to deliver 500 - 700 L of water ha⁻¹. About three time spray frequency was practiced per location. Spraying was practiced at 14-days intervals on each plot. Unsprayed plots were left for each replication as controls to allow maximum disease development. The first spray was started 55 days after transplanting when the first symptom of bacterial spot and late blight had appeared on tomato leaves and stems, respectively, within the plot.

2.3 Disease and Yield Parameter Assessment

Disease severity was assessed at 10-days interval in all locations. Twelve randomly pre-tagged tomato plants from the central rows of each plot were used for disease severity assessment and a total of six assessments were made per location. For all diseases, incidence (%) was determined by the rating of diseased plants per total number of plants assessed within the plot. Bacterial spot severity was assessed by estimating the percent leaf area affected (necrotic tissue) by bacterial spot using the Horsfall and Barratt rating scale (1945) where 1 = symptomless; 2 = a few necrotic spots; 3 = many spots, some coalescing; 4 = severe spotting and defoliation; and 5 = plant dead. Disease severity was calculated in Alabama by counting the number of lesions per 20 leaflets collected from each row per plot and expressing as number of lesions per cm² of leaflet area. Late blight severity was rated using a 0 to 9 disease scoring scale; where, 1 = no infections; 2 = 1-10% leaf area infected; 3 = 11-20% leaf area infected; 4 = 21-30% leaf area infected; 5 = 31-40% leaf area infected; 6 = 41-50% leaf area infected; 7 = 51-60% leaf area infected; 8 = 61-70% leaf area infected; and 9 = 71-100% leaf area infected as described by Horneburg & Becker (2011). Early blight severity was rated using a 1-12 disease scoring scale; where, 1 = no infections; 2 = 1-3% leaf area infected; 3 = 4-6% leaf area infected; 4 = 7-12% leaf area infected; 5 = 13-25% leaf area infected; 6 = 26-50% leaf area infected; 7 = 51-75% leaf area infected; 8 = 76-87% leaf area infected; 9 = 88-94% leaf area infected; 10 = 95-97% leaf area infected; 11 = 98-99% leaf area infected and 12 = 100% leaf area infected as described by Horsfall & Barratt (1945). Powdery mildew severity (percentage of the leaf surface covered with powdery mildew symptoms) was evaluated based on the scale of 0 to 6 (Yan *et al.*, 2006); where: 0, no visible pustule; 1, pustules on less than 1% of leaf surface; 2, 1 to 5% leaf surface covered with pustule; 3, 6 to 20% leaf surface covered with pustule; 4, 21 to 40% leaf surface covered with pustule; 5, 41 to 60% leaf surface covered with pustule; 6, more than 60% of leaf surface covered with pustule. Disease severity index was determined using following Formula: $\{(0A + 1B + 2C + 3D + 4E + 5F + 6G) / 6 (A + B + C + D + E + F + G)\} \times 100$, where A, B, C, D, E, F and G are the number of leaves with the disease index scores of 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6, respectively (Yan *et al.*, 2006). For all disease, the severity scores were transformed into percentage severity index (PSI) for analysis using the formula stated below (Wheeler, 1969).

$$PSI = \frac{\text{Sum of numerical ratings}}{\text{No. of plants scored} \times \text{maximum score on scale}} \times 100$$

The area under disease progress curve (AUDPC), the development of disease on a whole plant or part of the plant, for all diseases were computed from severity index values assessed at different days for each plot using the formula suggested by (Agrios, 2005). hereafter.

$$\text{AUDPC} = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} 0.5 (X_i + X_{i+1}) (t_{i-1} - t_i)$$

Where, n is the total number of disease assessments, t_i is the time of the i^{th} assessment in days from the first assessment date and x_i is the PSI of PB at the i^{th} assessment. AUDPC value was expressed in %-days because severity (x) is expressed in percent and time (t) in days.

Percentage fruit infection (PFI) (for late blight disease): It was recorded as percentage of tomato fruits infected per plant in the middle four rows as the average of 12 plants. Then the score was expressed as a percentage as follows:

$$\text{PFI} = \frac{\text{No. of fruits infected}}{\text{Total no. of fruits assessed}} \times 100$$

Data on visual observation on tomato leaves phytotoxicity was assessed during the growing period. Moreover, data on marketable, unmarketable, and total fruit yield of tomato were collected from the central rows of each plot from each location. Total yield was recorded as the weight of summation of marketable and unmarketable from each plot and expressed in kg ha^{-1} . Marketable fruit yield was determined by weighing marketable fruits (free from any damage, uniform in color, and ≥ 100 g in size) obtained from each plot and converted to kg ha^{-1} .

2.4 Data Analysis

Data on severity, AUDPC and yield-related parameters were subjected to analysis of variance to determine the treatment effects. The treatment means were separated using the Fishers protected least significance difference (LSD) test at 5% probability level (Gomez & Gomez, 1984). The data analyses were conducted using the general linear model procedure of the SAS software *version 9.2* (SAS, 2009).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Efficacy of Copper Plus WP on Bacterial Spot Development

Analysis of variance revealed that significant variations ($P < 0.001$) among and between the evaluated treatments on disease severity and AUDPC due to bacterial spot in the three locations (Table 1). However, no statistically significant difference on disease incidence was detected among and between the evaluated treatments, including unsprayed control plots, in all locations. Significant bacterial spot disease reductions were observed due to Copper Plus WP and Copper oxide 77% WP as compared to the unsprayed plots in the three locations. In this regard, the highest mean bacterial spot severity and AUDPC was recorded from unsprayed plots in the three locations. The lowest mean bacterial spot severity and AUDPC (except for Fura location) was recorded from Copper Plus WP sprayed plots as compared to the other sprayed and unsprayed plots across the locations (Table 1). At Fura location, no statistically significant variation was observed between the two pesticides concerning AUDPC (Table 1). Kucharek (1994) reported that chemical control of bacterial spot relies on multiple applications of copper- or streptomycin-based bactericides. Also, Sherf and MacNab (1986), and Majid *et al.* (2008) reported that “bacterial disease intensity was reduced only when a frequent application of systemic bactericide, which had a bactericidal properties in the product formulation. From the results of this trial Copper Plus WP is possible to deduce that three times foliar sprays at 14 days interval effectively reduce the magnitude of bacterial spot severity and AUDPC. The probable reasons for the effectiveness of Copper Plus WP might have better active ingredients in its formulation targeted for the disease. Under crosswise assessments, the overall bacterial spot development was highest at Fura, followed by Chano Chalba and Chano Chalba”. These could be explained by the favorable environmental conditions and the susceptibility of the variety as reported by Jones and Jones (1986) and Sherf and MacNab (1986). No phytotoxic symptoms such as yellowing and scorching on tomato leaves were observed after spraying with all the rates of pesticides applied.

Table 1. Efficacy of Copper Plus WP application on mean incidence, severity and area under disease progress curve of bacterial spot at Arba Minch (Chano Mile and Chano Chalba *kebeles*) and Mihirab Abaya (Fura *kebele*) during 2021 main cropping season

Treatment	Chano Mile			Chano Chalba			Fura		
	PDI _f (%)	PSI _f (%)	AUDPC (%-day)	PDI _f (%)	PSI _f (%)	AUDPC (%-day)	PDI _f (%)	PSI _f (%)	AUDPC (%-day)
Copper Plus WP	100	19.70c	211.75c	100	21.73c	223.12c	100	28.75b	269.47c
Copper oxide 77% WP	100	29.83b	364.42b	100	27.44b	357.25b	100	32.94b	427.28b
Unsprayed check	100	42.38a	583.13a	100	38.95a	549.93a	100	47.78a	570.10a
Mean	100	30.63	386.43	100	29.37	376.77	100	36.49	422.29
P-value	ns	< 0.001	< 0.0001	ns	< 0.01	< 0.0001	ns	< 0.001	< 0.0001
LSD (5%)	0.00	6.11	84.53	0.00	3.22	118.17	0.00	9.70	131.24
CV (%)	0.00	25.84	30.53	0.00	27.53	34.45	0.00	22.33	21.74

Means in the same column followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. PDI_f = Percent disease incidence at final assessment date; PSI_f = Percent severity index at final assessment date; AUDPC = Area under disease progress curve in %-day; CV = Coefficients of variation (%); and LSD = Least significant difference at $p < 0.05$ probability level

Table 2. Efficacy of Copper Plus WP application on mean percent fruit infection, incidence, severity and area under disease progress curve of late blight at Arba Minch (Chano Mile and Chano Chalba *kebeles*) and Mihirab Abaya (Fura *kebele*) during 2021 main cropping season

Treatment	Chano Mile				Chano Chalba				Fura			
	PFI (%)	PDI _f (%)	PSI _f (%)	AUDPC (%-day)	PFI (%)	PDI _f (%)	PSI _f (%)	AUDPC (%-day)	PFI (%)	PDI _f (%)	PSI _f (%)	AUDPC (%-day)
Copper Plus WP	10.38b	16.87b	23.61c	343.65b	7.69b	14.54b	21.65c	331.98b	6.25b	13.28b	16.04b	217.82b
Copper oxide 77% WP	15.09b	19.97b	29.07b	528.51b	8.61b	16.47b	26.53b	365.78b	9.79b	14.36b	16.30b	241.25b
Unsprayed check	24.39a	29.94a	38.60a	665.16a	14.09a	25.28a	32.33a	484.72a	14.01a	18.81a	26.29a	338.37a
Mean	16.62	22.26	30.43	512.44	10.13	18.76	26.84	394.16	10.02	15.48	19.54	265.81
P-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
LSD (5%)	8.14	9.01	2.18	245.08	8.01	6.83	3.34	175.56	4.15	5.05	6.64	79.72
CV (%)	4.44	7.88	10.12	20.54	6.94	10.44	12.12	23.90	8.98	13.16	14.36	27.66

Means in the same column followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. PFI = Percent fruit infection; PDI_f = Percent disease incidence at final assessment date; PSI_f = Percent severity index at final assessment date; AUDPC = Area under disease progress curve in %-day; CV = Coefficients of variation (%); and LSD = Least significant difference at $p < 0.05$ probability level

3.2 Efficacy of Copper Plus WP on Late Blight Development

Results obtained from analysis of variance concerning the efficacy of Copper Plus WP and Copper oxide 77% WP against late blight percent fruit infection, incidence, severity and AUDPC are shown in Table 2. Analysis of variance revealed that significant ($p < 0.001$) difference between the sprayed and unsprayed plots for percent fruit infection, incidence, severity and AUDPC in all locations (Table 2). In the three locations, the highest percent fruit infection, incidence, severity and AUDPC were recorded from unsprayed control plots. Conversely, the lowest percent fruit infection, incidence, severity and AUDPC were recorded on Copper Plus WP as compared to the unsprayed ones in all locations. However, the results obtained from Copper Plus WP sprayed plots were statistically similar (except for Chano Mile and Chano Chalba for severity) to Copper oxide 77% WP sprayed plots in the three locations (Table 1). At Chano Mile and Chano Chalba, significant differences were observed regarding late blight severity as compared to Copper oxide 77% WP-sprayed and unsprayed control plots (Table 2). Dillard *et al.* (1997) and (Tesfaye & Habtu (1986); Tsedeke, 2007; Derbew *et al.*, 2012). reported that “the intensity of late blight was low in the plots where frequently treated with fungicides as foliar spray practiced starting from disease onset. Crosswise comparisons showed the overall late blight epidemic development was highest at Chano Mile, followed by Chano Chalba and Fura, which could be explained by the prevailing relatively high temperature, relative humidity and extended plant wetness from frequent rain or dews during the period of infection”. Judelson & Blanco (2005), Majid *et al.* (2008) and Nowicki *et al.* (2013) reported that “heavy and frequent rainfall, along with high humidity and warm temperature favor infection and rapid development of late blight in the field”.

3.3 Efficacy of Copper Plus WP on Early Blight Development

Results obtained from the analysis of variance on the effect of pesticide having bactericidal and fungicidal properties on early blight incidence, severity, and AUDPC were presented in Table 3. According to the analysis of variance, significant ($P < 0.001$) difference in early blight disease development was observed between the evaluated pesticides, Copper Plus WP and Copper oxide 77% WP, in the three locations. Maximum mean early blight incidence, severity and AUDPC were recorded from unsprayed plots at the final date of assessment in the three locations. Minimum lowest mean early blight incidence, severity and AUDPC were noticed from plots sprayed with Copper Plus WP as compared to the other sprayed and unsprayed plots in the three locations. However, the results of incidence, severity and AUDPC (except Chano Chalba) obtained from Copper Plus WP sprayed plots were statistically similar to Copper oxide 77% WP-sprayed plots (Table 1). At Chano Chalba, a significant difference between the evaluated pesticides were observed, which showed the minimum mean AUDPC was recorded on Copper Plus WP sprayed plots. Keinath and DuBose (1996), (Agrios, 2005) and Mehari and Mohammed (2015) found that “maximum disease control with reduced early blight disease pressure was obtained from frequently sprayed newly introduced fungicides compared with the control plots. Generally, Copper Plus WP is possible to deduce that three times foliar sprays at 14 days intervals effectively reduce the magnitude of downy mildew severity. The probable reasons for the effectiveness of Copper Plus WP might have better active ingredients in its formulation targeted for early blight. Crosswise comparisons showed that the overall downy mildew epidemic development was highest at Fura, followed by Chano Mile and Chano Chalba, this might be high temperature and humidity at Fura” (Tsedeke, 2007; Derbew *et al.*, 2012).

3.4 Efficacy of Copper Plus WP on Powdery Mildew Development

Analysis of variance showed significant ($P < 0.001$) differences were observed between the sprayed and unsprayed control plots for incidence, severity and AUDPC in all locations (Table 4). The highest powdery mildew incidence, severity and AUDPC were recorded from unsprayed control plots in all locations. The lowest powdery mildew incidence, severity and AUDPC were noted from Copper Plus WP as compared to Copper oxide 77% WP sprayed and unsprayed control plots in the three locations (Table 4). Yildirim *et al.* (2002) reported that “the powdery mildew pressure on tomato was low where plots treated with newly introduced fungicides as compared to the existing fungicides (old one) as foliar spray applications during the growing periods. Crosswise comparisons showed the highest powdery mildew epidemic development was observed at Fura, followed by Chano Chalba and Chano Mile, which could be explained by the prevailing relatively temperature from frequent rain or dews during the period of infection”. Mieslerová and Lebeda (1999) reported that “heavy rainfall followed by high warm temperature favor infection and rapid development of tomato powdery mildew in the field”.

Table 3. Efficacy of Copper Plus WP application on mean incidence, severity and area under disease progress curve of early blight at Arba Minch (Chano Mile and Chano Chalba *kebeles*) and Mihirab Abaya (Fura *kebele*) during 2021 main cropping season

Treatment	Chano Mile			Chano Chalba			Fura		
	PDI _f (%)	PSI _f (%)	AUDPC (%-day)	PDI _f (%)	PSI _f (%)	AUDPC (%-day)	PDI _f (%)	PSI _f (%)	AUDPC (%-day)
Copper Plus WP	37.34b	29.78b	435.91b	32.58b	32.93b	514.52c	50.13b	35.48b	605.71b
Copper oxide 77% WP	46.06b	34.31b	588.57b	39.04b	40.89b	637.45b	57.11b	39.67b	651.44b
Unsprayed check	76.83a	53.59a	885.74a	79.76a	52.40a	830.13a	78.88a	56.75a	895.13a
Mean	53.41	39.23	636.74	50.46	42.07	660.70	62.04	43.96	717.43
P-value	< 0.001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.0001	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.0001
LSD (5%)	13.28	10.46	262.11	20.33	9.22	168.56	8.38	5.49	111.24
CV (%)	28.98	22.24	25.84	14.11	16.32	19.25	24.70	17.33	14.72

Means in the same column followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. PDI_f = Percent disease incidence at final assessment date; PSI_f = Percent severity index at final assessment date; AUDPC = Area under disease progress curve in %-day; CV = Coefficients of variation (%); and LSD = Least significant difference at $p < 0.05$ probability level

Table 4. Efficacy of Copper Plus WP application on mean incidence, severity and area under disease progress curve of powdery mildew at Arba Minch (Chano Mile and Chano Chalba *kebeles*) and Mihirab Abaya (Fura *kebele*) during 2021 main cropping season

Treatment	Chano Mile			Chano Chalba			Fura		
	PDI _f (%)	PSI _f (%)	AUDPC (%-day)	PDI _f (%)	PSI _f (%)	AUDPC (%-day)	PDI _f (%)	PSI _f (%)	AUDPC (%-day)
Copper Plus WP	13.05c	5.68c	108.28c	13.56c	10.44c	107.82c	17.81c	12.48c	144.14c
Copper oxide 77% WP	24.70b	17.86b	169.86b	18.73b	17.59b	186.46b	28.51b	26.10b	254.69b
Unsprayed check	32.23a	24.03a	194.43a	25.23a	25.60a	238.15a	34.92a	40.68a	279.00a
Mean	23.32	15.86	157.52	19.17	17.88	177.47	27.08	26.42	225.94
P-value	< 0.001	< 0.0001	< 0.001	< 0.01	< 0.0001	< 0.001	< 0.01	< 0.0001	< 0.001
LSD (5%)	7.06	11.23	46.39	3.20	5.47	63.23	8.01	11.05	82.48
CV (%)	11.06	17.41	21.31	8.87	13.82	34.12	18.88	27.89	14.66

Means in the same column followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. PDI_f = Percent disease incidence at final assessment date; PSI_f = Percent severity index at final assessment date; AUDPC = Area under disease progress curve in %-day; CV = Coefficients of variation (%); and LSD = Least significant difference at $p < 0.05$ probability level

Table 5. Effect of Copper Plus WP application on mean marketable, unmarketable and total fruit yield of tomato at Arba Minch (Chano Mile and Chano Chalba kebeles) and Mihirab Abaya (Fura kebele) during 2021 main cropping season

Treatment	Chano Mile			Chano Chalba			Fura		
	MFY (kg/ha)	UMFY (kg/ha)	TFY (kg/ha)	MFY (kg/ha)	UMFY (kg/ha)	TFY (kg/ha)	MFY (kg/ha)	UMFY (kg/ha)	TFY (kg/ha)
Copper Plus WP	31367.37a	1568.28b	32935.65a	30134.60a	1378.12b	31512.73a	28948.19a	1181.92b	30130.11a
Copper oxide 77% WP	26899.17a	1662.34b	28561.51a	25167.56a	1602.82b	26770.37a	25288.25a	1567.79b	26856.04a
Unsprayed	767.98	3222.91a	3990.88b	1525.87b	3739.53a	5265.40b	6541.50b	3322.91a	9864.41b
Mean	19678.17	2151.18	21829.35	18942.68	2240.16	21182.83	20259.32	2024.21	22283.52
P-value	<0.001	<0.0001	<0.001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.001	<0.0001
LSD (5%)	6507.25	869.39	7376.64	10616.00	1662.49	12278.49	8100.48	1044.10	9144.58
CV (%)	18.34	6.44	20.05	20.00	9.15	16.16	10.46	4.96	16.68

Means in the same column followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. MFY = Marketable fruit yield in kg/ha; UMFY = Unmarketable fruit yield in kg/ha; TFY = Total fruit yield in kg/ha; CV = Coefficients of variation (%); and LSD = Least significant difference at $p < 0.05$ probability level

3.5 Yield Related Parameters

Analysis of variance revealed that marketable, unmarketable, and total fruit yields of tomato significantly ($p < 0.001$) affected by the application of Copper Plus WP and Copper oxide 77% WP in the three locations (Table 5). The highest marketable and total bulb yields and the lowest unmarketable fruit yields of tomato were noted from Copper Plus WP applied plots in the three locations. However, the aforementioned parameters recorded from Copper Plus WP sprayed plots were not statistically different from Copper oxide 77% WP sprayed plots across the locations. The lowest marketable and total fruit yields and the highest unmarketable fruit yields of tomato were noticed from the unsprayed control plots in all locations (Table 4). At Fura, a relatively lower yield advantage over the other locations might be due to the high pressure of bacterial spot, early blight and powdery mildew during the epidemic periods; also, the medium effects of environmental factors were considered. Overall, it is possible to conclude the bactericide Copper Plus WP played a significant role in increasing tomato fruit yields, which could be attributed to their favorable effects on tomato yield contributing parameters such as a number of healthy leaves and total leaf area index, while creating adverse effects for different metabolic activities of the target pathogen like a breakdown of host membrane and biochemical processes and suppress high disease pressure. (Keinath and DuBose (1996), Dillard *et al.* (1997) and Yildirim *et al.* (2002) reported that “the application of effective bactericide and fungicide protects the tomato from bacterial spot, late blight, early blight and powdery mildew epidemics and increases yield and yield components” (Jones *et al.*, 1986).

4. Conclusions

Evidence showed that Copper Plus WP (Copper oxychloride 30% + Azoxystrobin 10%) at the rate of 1 kilogram per hectare diluted with 400 liters of water played a pronounced effect in minimizing the epidemic development of bacterial spot, late blight, early blight and powdery mildew, and subsequently increase fruit yield of tomato as compared to Copper oxide 77% WP across the locations. No foliar toxic effect was observed from the effect of any tested fungicides during the growing period. Generally, results showed that the newly tested fungicide, Copper Plus WP at the rate of 1 kilogram per hectare with 400 L water effectively controlled the aforementioned diseases. Hence, Copper Plus WP was found highly effective and therefore it is recommended for registration for the management of these diseases.

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence)

Author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.) and text-to-image generators have been used during the writing or editing of this manuscript.

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Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- Agrios, G. N. (2005). *Plant pathology* (5th ed.). Elsevier Academic Press.
<https://www.elsevier.com/books/plant-pathology/agrios/978-0-12-044565-3>
- Anonymous. (2011). *Indian horticulture database: Major tomato producing countries in the world*. New Delhi, India. <http://nhb.gov.in/area-pro/database-2011.pdf>
- Bauchet, G., & Causse, M. (2012). Genetic diversity in tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) and its wild relatives. In M. Caliskan (Ed.), *Genetic diversity in plants* (pp. 133–162). InTech Publisher.
<https://doi.org/10.5772/33073>

- Derbew Belew, Mohammed, A., & Amina, J. G. (2012). Yield and quality of indeterminate tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) varieties with staking methods in Jimma. *Singapore Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(2), 33–46. <https://doi.org/10.3923/sjsres.2012.33.46>
- Dillard, H. R., Johnston, S. A., Cobb, A. C., & Hamilton, G. H. (1997). An assessment of fungicide benefits for the control of fungal diseases of processing tomatoes in New York and New Jersey. *Plant Disease*, 81, 677–681. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PDIS.1997.81.6.677>
- Gomez, K. A., & Gomez, A. A. (1984). *Statistical procedures for agricultural research* (2nd ed.). John Wiley and Sons. <https://www.wiley.com/en-us/Statistical+Procedures+for+Agricultural+Research%2C+2nd+Edition-p-9780471870920>
- Horneburg, B., & Becker, H. C. (2011). Selection for *Phytophthora* field resistance in the F2 generation of organic outdoor tomatoes. *Euphytica*, 180, 357–367. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10681-011-0384-3>
- Horsfall, J. G., & Barratt, R. W. (1945). An improved grading system for measuring plant disease. *Phytopathology*, 35, 655. <https://doi.org/10.1094/Phyto-35-655>
- Jones, J. B., Pohronezny, K. L., Stall, R. E., & Jones, J. P. (1986). Survival of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *Vesicatoria* in Florida on tomato crop residue, weeds, seeds, and volunteer tomato plants. *Phytopathology*, 76, 430–434. <https://doi.org/10.1094/Phyto-76-430>
- Judelson, H. S., & Blanco, F. A. (2005). The spores of *Phytophthora*: Weapons of the plant destroyer. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 3, 47–58. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro1064>
- Keinath, A. P., DuBose, V. B., & Rathwell, P. J. (1996). Efficiency and economics of three fungicidal application schedules for early blight control and yield of fresh market tomato. *Plant Disease*, 80, 1277–1282. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PD-80-1277>
- Kucharek, T. (1994). *Bacterial spot of tomato and pepper*. Plant pathology fact sheet PP-3. University of Florida. <https://ufdc.ufl.edu/IR00005294/00001>
- Majid, R. F., Heather, L. M., & Hamid, A. (2008). Genetics, genomics and breeding of late blight and early blight resistance in tomato. *Plant Sciences*, 27, 75–107. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07352680802147353>
- McCarter, S. M., Jones, J. B., Gitaitis, R. D., & Smitley, D. R. (1983). Survival of *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *tomato* in association with tomato seed, soil, host tissue, and epiphytic weed hosts in Georgia. *Phytopathology*, 73, 1393–1398. <https://doi.org/10.1094/Phyto-73-1393>
- Mehari Desta, & Mohammed Yesuf. (2015). Efficacy and economics of fungicides and their application schedule for early blight (*Alternaria solani*) management and yield of tomato at South Tigray, Ethiopia. *Journal of Plant Pathology and Microbiology*, 6, 268. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2157-7471.1000268>
- Nowicki, M., Lichocka, M., Nowakowska, M., Kłosińska, U., Golik, P., & Kozik, E. U. (2013). A simple dual stain for detailed investigations of plant–fungal pathogen interactions. *Vegetable Crops Research Bulletin*, 77, 61–74. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10032-012-0016-z>
- SAS Institute. (2009). *SAS/STAT user's guide* (Version 9.2). SAS Institute Inc.
- Sherf, A. F., & MacNab, A. A. (1986). *Vegetable diseases and their control* (2nd ed.). John Wiley & Sons. <https://www.wiley.com/en-us/Vegetable+Diseases+and+Their+Control,+2nd+Edition-p-9780471058601>
- Tesfaye Tedla, & Habtu Assefa. (1986). A review of vegetable disease research in Ethiopia. In T. Abate (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 1st Crop Protection Symposium* (pp. 495–518). Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. <https://agris.fao.org/search/en/providers/122600/records/647750d35eb437ddff744bc3>
- Tsedek Abate. (2007). *Focusing on agricultural research to address development needs: Direction for agricultural research in Ethiopia*. Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- United States Department of Agriculture [USDA]. (2005). *Agricultural research service, nutrient database for standard reference* (Release 18). <http://www.ars.usda.gov/ba/bhnrc/ndl>
- Wheeler, B. J. (1969). *An introduction to plant diseases*. John Wiley and Sons. https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/10.1079/cabicompndium_C000000000021
- Yan, Z., Dolstra, O., Prins, T. W., Stam, P., & Visser, P. B. (2006). Assessment of partial resistance to powdery mildew *Podosphaera pannosa* in a tetraploid rose population using a spore suspension inoculum method. *European Journal of Plant Pathology*, 114, 301–308. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10658-005-5995-x>

Yildirim, A., Onogur, E., & Irshad, M. (2002). Investigations on the efficacy of some natural chemicals against powdery mildew [*Uncinula necator* (Schw.) Burr.] of grape. *Journal of Phytopathology*, 150, 697–702. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1439-0434.2002.00827.x>

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